

More Than a Poet? Why Russian Writers Didn't Blog on the 2008 Elections

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On 2 March 2008, *Livejournal* user *snorapp*—alias Linor Goralik—posted an entry on an upcoming poetry event (*snorapp 2008*). On 3 March, *galkovsky*, also known as Dmitrii Galkovskii, reported on his participation in an Internet conference (*galkovsky 2008*). On the same day, readers of Dmitrii Babil'skii's blog were treated to a theatre review (*paslen 2008*). On March 4, Tat'iana Tolstaia's blog referred to a gigantic pie with “little cherries and peaches,” presented at the Baltic Book Fair in Riga (*tanyant 2008*). A few hours later, Evgenii Grishkovets blogged on “the theme of spring” and his recent performances (*e-grishkovets 2008*). The next day, Dmitrii Vodennikov linked readers to his column on Walt Whitman (*vodennikov 2008*). And on March 13, Aleksei Slapovskii posted a story about a man with two brains (*slapovsky 2008*).

Written by a selection of Russia's most prominent literary bloggers,¹ these seven apparently unconnected entries share one vital feature. Each was the blogger's first post after the presidential elections of 2 March. Yet each deals with anything—poems, plays, spring, or even a cherry pie—but the elections. On days when traditional Russian and international media buzzed with news about the newly elected president, what explains such a persistent silence on election-related themes in the literary blogosphere?

This essay explores factors that may account for the absence of literary-blog discussions about Russia's 2008 elections. At first blush, the lack of such discussions appears to negate a pervasive assertion in RuNet research: where traditional media are not always spared censorship, the Russian Internet has purportedly become a platform for free political debate (Leibov, *c.f.* Davydov 2007; Gusejnov 2006, 12; Schmidt, Teubener, Konradova 2006, 15). Russian bloggers, so experts claim, devote substantially more attention to politics than non-

¹ This cross-section includes literary bloggers whose popularity can be measured based on exceptionally high reader and comment numbers (such as Evgenii Grishkovets' or Tat'iana Tolstaia's blog), blogs with a high symbolical status in intellectual and literary circles (see Galina 2007 and Shevelev 2008), or written by prominent mainstream media intellectuals. The last category includes Linor Goralik, who writes for *Novoe literaturnoe obozrenie* and *openspace.ru*). Goralik is, strictly speaking, not a “Russian” blogger. Born in the Ukraine, she spent part of her youth in Israel and does not hold a Russian passport. Nevertheless, I chose to include her in this selection since Russian is her native language, she grew up in the Soviet Union, and she has been based in Moscow since 2001.

Russians (Fitzpatrick, *c.f.* Kosterina 2008). Alexander Etkind even goes so far as to call *Livejournal*—the service that hosts most Russian blogs, including those mentioned here—a “new kind” of freethinkers’ “ghetto” where Russian intellectuals seek “refuge” from the increasingly restrictive world of more traditional media (Etkind 2006). However, if these seven renowned bloggers were silent on the results of the elections, then perhaps the Russian blogosphere is not as politically charged as we consider it to be?

The picture becomes more complex when one considers the same bloggers’ reactions to a more recent significant political event: the war between Russia and Georgia. When Russian troops entered South Ossetia on 9 August 2008, some of the blogs mentioned above did emerge as vehicles for political expression and discussion. On 10 August, Dmitrii Galkovskii posted a lengthy entry on the conflict (galkovsky 2008). On the same day, Evgenii Grishkovets gave an extensive explanation of why he supported Georgia, but disapproved of Saakashvili (e-grishkovets 2008). On 12 August, Linor Goralik attended her readers to an analysis of media reports on the war; ten days later, she dissected the rhetoric used in its public discussion (snorapp 2008). Dmitrii Vodennikov referred to the war in passing, if only in posts on literary-linguistic issues, on 13 and 20 August (vodennikov 2008). And on 7 September, Aleksei Slapovskii suggested that the tension between Russian and Western-European-cum-American leaders, fuelled by the war, lent new meaning to the phrase “[Russia,] You are alone in this world!” in the national anthem (slapovsky 2008).

In other words, other political events did spawn a generous string of reactions in the literary blogosphere, and the RuNet in no way lost its function as platform for political thinking in the past year. Neither can one attribute the authors’ political silence in March to fear of censorship. On the one hand, by today state interference in the Russian media landscape has become an accepted fact. That the World Wide Web is not entirely free from Kremlin intervention anymore is no secret either. In the words of Robert A. Saunders, the Russian Internet is not prone to censorship as such, but the Kremlin does exert a “soft approach of manipulation,” which “diffuses the attraction of political activity among the people” (*c.f.* Solash 2008). Apart from soft power exertion, new laws against inciting hatred allow authorities to implement “harder” forms of intervention as well. Last August, for instance, a blogger was sentenced to 18 months of conditional imprisonment for using violent language against police officers in his blog (Lenta.ru 2008).

On the other hand, despite ongoing rumors, there is no concrete evidence that politically critical bloggers are censored. The August verdict, albeit severe, does not differ substantially from similar charges against hatred-inciting blog comments outside of Russia. Around the time that the Russian blogger faced his verdict—to cite but one example—a German court was busy issuing a similar conviction for invoking hatred in a blog entry (O’Connell 2008; also *c.f.* Rutten 2008). Moreover, as Henrike Schmidt has shown, the relationship between the authorities and Russia’s blog community is too complex to reduce to a one-sided power play (Schmidt 2002). Not surprisingly, “our” seven authors do not withhold from adopting a downright critical tone in political entries. In his 10 August post on the events in Georgia, Galkovskii calls the authorities “Kremlin dreamers” (galkovsky 2008); on the same day, Grishkovets expresses pro-Georgia sentiments that evidently clash with the official perspective (e-grishkovets 2008).

With this in mind, fear of censorship does not adequately explain the writers' silence on the elections. Which begs the question: is it motivated, perhaps, by more pragmatic considerations? Did these writers refrain from the act of political commenting because it might decrease their popularity among readers? A closer look at the blogs shows that this explanation is equally implausible. Galkovskii's comment on the Russo-Georgian war generated 802 comments, as opposed to an average of 383 on the preceding five entries.² Grishkovets' discussion of the war led to 1190 comments, as opposed to 209 comments on average for the five preceding posts. If aggressive at times, then the extensive reactions do amount to lively dialogues with the authors, which are likely to enhance rather than damage their blogs' popularity. Thus, political (self-)censorship or lack of audience demand cannot have possibly dictated the bloggers' choice to be silent about the elections. What then, motivated the authors in question to remain silent *in toto* on this particular occasion?

In part, the collective silence of these and other literary bloggers must be explained by a simple unwillingness to devote energy to a publicly staged event—one that had been meticulously planned by political technologists. Practically all oppositional and foreign media have questioned the fairness of the election process, and reports on propagandistic media exploitations circulated ever since 2007. Within the blogosphere, critical bloggers sardonically congratulated Dmitrii Medvedev with his election as president as early as December 2007 (Newsru.com 2007). Their sarcasm reflects a general public distrust of—and disinterest in—politics in today's Russia. As polls held in the past two years suggest, the current level of political engagement among Russian citizens is extremely low. Most respondents see politics as a “closed-off space,” which they do not support or trust but don't actively oppose either, as long as it doesn't affect their physical and material well-being (White 2008). “Everything is useless here [*U nas vse bespolezno*]”: thus sounds a favourite answer to inquiries about political participation (ibid.).

Political involvement does occasionally manifest, such as last August during the Russian-Georgian war. Even if a majority of Russians was aware of increasing tensions in the South-Ossetian conflict, the very suddenness and scale of its escalation in August were in no way anticipated by the general public. When fierce anti-Russian reactions from the West added up to the existing consternation, the events triggered a vivid public debate. But such debates are incidental rather than everyday practice. On a day-to-day basis, there is “simply no demand for political projects” at the moment (Kuznetsov 2008).

How does this relate to the literary bloggers? It would stretch too far to draw a direct parallel between their stance towards the elections and the general political disengagement: the polls mentioned above were held mainly in provincial cities, and the majority of respondents represented radically different social categories than the urbanized intellectuals at stake here. This notwithstanding, the bloggers' behaviour mirrors that of the average Russian as rendered in the polls. In their recent blog posts they, too, tended to opt for disengagement and retreat into non-political spheres. They, too, refused to invest energy in elections which were not going to be affected by public criticism anyway. And several of them, too, exchanged their

² Throughout this essay, I refer to the number of comments that a post had generated by 15 September 2008, including contributions by the authors themselves.

aversion for political involvement when faced with particularly unexpected or emotionally compelling political developments.

But the silence in March might also be explained by a more “literary” factor than the feeling that political engagement is pointless. This explanation can be found in statements by the writers themselves. Tat’iana Tolstaia defines her blog as a distinct discursive space, one devised—as she says in a comment on her 18 December 2007 post—“for answers, contacts, and other practical trifles” (tanyant 2007). In other words, tanyant is simply not set up as an instrument for political discussion. What attracts the author in blogging is what commentators have branded Russian literary blogs’ “colloquialness” (*razgovornost*) (Polotovskii 2006) or “near-literariness” (*okololiteraturnost*) (Kaspe & Smurova 2002): a tendency, rather than towards “serious writing,” to collect “sympathetic reactions, everyday advice, literary instructions, offers to help, to bring a few tangerines, to correct the second paragraph, and to replace some words” (*ibid.*). What Tolstaia expects from her blog is precisely that: an informal chat, or a dialogue with her readers, without having to comment on topical social or political events.

If Tolstaia’s refusal to touch upon political events may be confined to her blog, then Linor Goralik is not interested in the role of political or social commentator whatsoever, neither in off- or online writings. That someone of Ukrainian descent, who does not hold a Russian passport, is not particularly engaged in the election of Russia’s new president is hardly surprising. But Goralik’s hesitation to confine her political views is not limited to the election period. When she does write a linguistic analysis that refers to the Russian-Georgian war, she explains that—rather than in politics in themselves—she is “as always, interested in language and details” (snorapp 2008). And Dmitrii Baviľ’skii, when asked on 12 August by one reader why he did not blog on the recent war, refused to adopt the pose of political observer by asserting: “all of that will pass” (paslen 2008). In short, the authors in question express interest in practical issues, in linguistic matters, in themes that are less ephemeral than politics—but they simply do not wish to provide political analyses. And, one could ask, why should they? These are, after all, literary writers above all. Then why expect them to blog about the elections in the first place?

More than anything else, the silence on the elections by these and other literary bloggers deflates the myth of Russian literature as a vehicle for political debate. The idea that there is a uniquely Russian trend in which writers appear as “political commentator, tribune, even religious prophet” (Hosking 1997, 293-294) may be disputed by many a scholar today, but is still a persistent ingredient of public and academic discourse on Russia. Of the writers considered here, some agree with that stance. Galkovskii and Grishkovets are a case in point. The latter consciously paraphrases Evgenii Evtushenko’s illustrious phrase “in Russia, a poet is more than a poet” when introducing himself to Mikhail Saakashvili with the statement: “I am a writer, who, in Russia, is more than a writer” (e-grishkovets 2008). But others, such as Tat’iana Tolstaia, Dmitrii Vodennikov or Dmitrii Baviľ’skii, unerringly refrain from articulating political ideas, whether in their blogs or elsewhere. The stark contrast between these authors leaves little doubt that there is no such thing as a “uniquely” Russian, “politicized” literary culture.

In itself, this awareness is not new. An angry Viktor Erofeev already openly defied Evtushenko’s more-than-a-poet device in 1990, in the *Literaturnaia Gazeta*, where he stated that

for Russian writers, it was time “to finally return to literature”—one which would be “no more and no less than *literature*” (Erofeev 1996, 434; italics in the original). Erofeev, and with him many others, have argued that a generalizing claim such as Evtushenko’s is, by definition, impossible. Still others sustain the generalization, but paradoxically invert it: thus, one famous curator recently claimed that writers’ social prestige has dwindled to such an extent that in post-Soviet Russia, “a poet is less than a poet” (Backstein 2007, 47).

But in twenty-first century Russian literature, what *is* new is the possibility to invalidate the “more-than-a-writer” myth by analyzing blogs. It is the blog which shows that a generalizing claim of this kind is principally erratic. In its capacity of online publication tool, the weblog indicates the precise date and time when an entry was posted. It allows the writer to react immediately—without intervention by a publisher or agent—on topical political, economic, social, or cultural events in a public setting. It endows new opportunities to the reader as well: he or she can ascertain—with a few clicks of the mouse and immediately after the event in question—whether different writers opt for such a reaction or not.

Because of these media-specific features, we can now affirm that none of the seven authors discussed here chose to switch on the computer and react in writing to the news that must have permeated their intellectual environments in early March 2008. Because of the here-and-now character of blogs, we know that these writers chose not to write about politics at the time. We know that some of them did feel an urge to react a few months later, when faced with a less predictable type of political turmoil. And we know that some of them refrained from political comments on both occasions. More so than paper publications, their blogs help us realize that, just as in any country, in Russia sometimes writers long to be “more than writers,” while at other times, they do not.

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